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Abstract Relationship between the acquisition of foreign languages and motivation was studied both by local and foreign scientists. Studies have shown that it is motivation that makes it easy and effective to learn foreign languages. This article discusses the importance of motivation in foreign language learning process in the schools and the influencing factors. The higher the internal and external motivation of a student, the easier it will be for him to overcome the language barriers. Thus, increasing students' motivation for language learning before the classes is crucial, and this motivation make the student move forward like the motor moves a car, as Dornyei (1998) stated. This, in turn, requires a foreign language teacher to have a motivational approach to each lesson, taking into account the age, interest, level and the aptitude of a student.

Key Words: Motivation, Motivational theories, Language Learning, Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation, Influence

Introduction

Learning foreign languages is one of the key factors in the socio-economic and general cultural development of a society. Especially, in the age of globalization the role of learning foreign languages has become crucial to establish and strengthen socio-economic and cultural ties among the countries all over the world. Therefore, the interest and the demand for learning the foreign languages, particularly, English which is considered to be the world communicative language has increased

significantly. The new political and socio-economic changes have taken place in Uzbekistan over the past five years. The country's desire for active and effective cooperation with western countries, have had a significant impact on expanding the function of a foreign language as a subject and led to a review of goals, objectives and content of teaching and learning English. Uzbekistan's policy of openness, its active entry into the world market, the new political situation, the expansion of international cooperation and international relations make it necessary for current specialists to acquire more than one foreign language. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated: "It is time to establish a new system of teaching foreign languages in our country, which will be a solid foundation for the future. Since we have set ourselves the goal of building a competitive state, from now on graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must be fluent in at least 2 foreign languages. This strict requirement should become the main criterion of the activity of the head of each educational institution [1]." The officials in Uzbekistan use the term "foreign language" rather than "second language", it's because the second language isn't officially accepted by the government. Russian is also used as a means of communication but it is typical to the upper generation who studied and worked in the former Soviet Union when learning and using the language was priority. But now learning English is more popular among the youth due to the wide possibilities in business, in education and in technology. The attitude towards the learning foreign language among the teenagers has increased significantly compared to 5 years ago. Uzbekistan reopened to the world by changing its internal and external policy especially in the field of education. The government allowed prominent foreign universities open their local branches in Uzbekistan and successfully started fruitful cooperation with Foreign Agencies like British Council and American Embassy to support language learning among the population. The government encouraged learners to acquire the foreign languages by giving various facilities and support them financially. In consequence, these

measures directly impact on students' language learning motivation and help them to successfully acquire the foreign languages.

Motivation in foreign language learning

We often use the term "motivation" in the lessons to help students to reach the intended goal of the lessons. Terms such as "motivation" and "motivate students" are the most commonly used words in teachers' vocabulary. Besides, the terms "motivation" and "motivator" have already become a popular in the business community of our country. However, in the article we would like to discuss about the importance of motivation in learning foreign languages. We all know that knowing a foreign language helps any person to increase his or her chances in achieving his or her goals. We have also heard a lot about the generally accepted notion that fast, easy, and perfect language acquisition depends on a person's passion, motivation, and action. But there are different opinions on what factors influence a learner's interest in language learning and motivation. Although the problem of increasing students' motivation is relevant to every subject, it is especially, more important in learning a foreign language. Motivation is therefore is seen as the main driving force in the study of a foreign language, the motives relating to the subjective world of the individual and are determined by his inner motives [2]. Accordingly, a person can learn a foreign language if he really needs it, that is, if he is encouraged. According to linguist Z. Dornyei (2013), motivation is a type of desire to learn. Dornyei (1998), also emphasizes that in order to teach a foreign language in a learning environment, at first students are supposed to have a desire to learn the language and that motivation is the main impulse to start learning a foreign language and further it becomes the main driving force to continue the long-term learning process.

What is motivation and its importance in learning foreign languages

Although scholars around the world claim that motivation plays an important role in foreign language teaching, they have different interpretations of the terms

regarding to “motive” and “motivation”. Let us now consider the scholars' interpretations of this term. Scholars have defined the concept of "motive" as follows: A. Maslow believes that the motive is a set of needs, K. Vilyunas considers the conditions of existence as a motive, G. Kovalev explains motives as the moral and political relationships, J. Godefroy states motive is a goal which the subject is supposed to reach [3]. Therefore, this concept requires a comprehensive approach, taking into account all possible aspects. Wikipedia defines "motive" as follows: “A motive is the cause that moves people to induce a certain action.” [4].

Motivation is also interpreted differently as a mental phenomenon: in one case - as a set of supporting and directing, such as determinants of behavior (K. Madsen, 1959; J. Godefroy, 1992), in another case - as a set of motives (K.K. Platonov, 1986), and in another case - as an impulse that triggers the activity of the organism and determines its direction. In addition, motivation is also seen as a process of mental regulation of certain activities (M.Sh. Magomed-Eminov, 1998), as a process of movement of motives and as a mechanism for the emergence, direction and methods of specific activities (I.A. Jidaryan, 1976), the line is described by scholars as a set of motives that are the trigger for actions (V.K. Vilyunas, 1990) [5]. Thus, based on the research and conclusions of scientists, we can give the following definitions of the concepts of “motive” and “motivation”. The concept of "motive" (Lat. Movere - action, push) means the encouragement of action, the impetus to cause, and factor of action and behavior. Motives can be different: interest in the meaning and process of activity, duty before society, self-affirmation, and so on. Motivation is a set of motivating factors that determine an individual's activity; these include motives, needs, incentives, and situational factors that determine human behavior.

The term motivation refers to a system of rewards that can have a positive impact on the level of proficiency of the subject and the effectiveness of the development of skills and abilities. Therefore, the formation of the learning motive in the methodology of teaching foreign languages is always an important priority not

only for the whole educational process, but also for every single teacher as well. Motivation is an important part of achieving any goal. This is a significant factor that has a positive impact on any learning process, especially learning a foreign language. Salvin (Rehman et al., 2014) described motivation as an internal process that activates, directs, and maintains behavior over time. Motivation is not stable, it tends to change depending on the situation and also changes over time (Gass and Selinker, 2008). Reese and Walker (Reece and Walker, 2001) argue that motivation is a key factor in the process of learning a foreign language. They also stressed that low-income students with high motivation are more likely to succeed than smart but low-motivated students [6]. Sometimes students come to school with high motivation, and in these cases, the main task of a foreign language teacher is to maintain the motivation of students, to prevent them from falling into demotivation, and to maximize it.

Types of motivation

Gardner (1985) divided the motivation factors in foreign language learning into two types: integrative motivation and instrumental motivation. Both types of motivation, taking into account different approaches, "have an impact on the successful acquisition of a foreign language [7]." According to Brown (1994), "integrative motivation" refers to language learning for personal development and cultural improvement, i.e., the learner wants to learn a language in order to understand, communicate and integrate into that community. Masgoret and Gardner (2003) classify students with integrative motivation as students who are open to other language communities, as well as those who tend to learn throughout the learning process and who always have a positive attitude toward others.

In addition, integratively motivated learners are more persistent in the learning process, especially when faced with challenges or challenging tasks. This is because they value their learning motives, ie the need and reasons for learning a language, as a personal quality, and this is why integratively motivated students do their best to

learn foreign languages. Gardner et al (1983) described instrumental motivation as “learning for profit”. These types of learners learn a foreign language to gain a certain pragmatic benefit rather than social significance. Therefore, we can also assume that students’ instrumental goals in learning a foreign language are a focused approach to achieving certain goals that are not related to interpersonal relationships. The instrumentally motivated students learn English to get the external reward such as gaining scholarship as well as successfully participating in international projects or various programs just to get material benefit. The instrumental goals encourage students to learn foreign languages not only in their studies but also for their future career, such as working in reputable companies, and gaining high-paying jobs. These instrumental goals can serve to increase learners' social status or self-confidence, as well as open up business opportunities and motivate growth in work, and lead to positive changes in education (Saville, 2006). In view of the above considerations, we can conclude that instrumental motivation consists of a group of factors related to external rewards such as passing exams, financial awards, good position or successful completion of school, getting a well-paid job.

Scientists have also identified two other types of motivation: intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Dyornei (1998) gives the following definition of internal and external motivation. Intrinsic motivation motivates a person to engage in a particular activity because they like it and enjoy it. External motivation is the result of external influences, such as gaining a reward (money, material wealth), gaining people's attention or escaping punishment [8]. For example, if a tennis player plays tennis in order to win a prize, it will be influenced by external motivation, and if he plays tennis because he likes it, it will be motivated by internal motivation. In the same way, a student's diligent study for the purpose of getting a good grade or fear of getting a low grade is considered to be the result of external motivation. It has been universally acknowledged by scientists that work done under the influence of internal motivation is more effective. R.M. Ryan and E.L. Deci

argues that inner motivation is important because a person's strong inner desire to learn and acquire knowledge directs them towards a goal. External motivation can change significantly in an individual's ability to work independently and self-control as a result of external factors. Accordingly, external motivation can also be expressed in several ways, in the first case, students with external motivation perform an action in a forced, reluctant and dissatisfied state, and in the second case, a person's compulsive desire might be reflected in their inner will and in turn, trigger the action [9].

What motivates Uzbek students to learn a foreign language

Based on the above scientific grounds, it can be stated that Uzbek students have an instrumental motivation to learn foreign languages. The reason for this is that students learn foreign languages, especially English, not for the integration, but as an instrument for achieving their future goals. The main goals and objectives of teaching foreign languages, especially English, to students of general secondary schools, academic lyceums and vocational schools based on the full satisfaction of such needs as a successful pass. Especially in the current era of globalization and the ongoing reforms in our country, the attitude to the teaching of English has become more important than ever.

Factors affecting motivation

Obviously, the effectiveness of a foreign language teaching process depends on many factors, but motivation plays a vital role in a foreign language classes. Motives and motivation are the driving force of the learning process.

The question of how a foreign language teacher can develop students' interest in learning English and how to maintain that interest in the long run is always troubling. It should be borne in mind that learning motivation is closely related to social factors, as many factors influencing learning motivation are formed under the influence of society and social conditions. "Because learning motivation is largely socially

conditioned, there are many opportunities to manage it in the pedagogical process[10]."

Factors influencing motivation are not limited to social factors, but can also be influenced by personality, age, culture, and many other relevant factors. Taking all of the above facts into account, I'd like to agree to the following statement "in each case, the motivation to learn a foreign language is ultimately a combination of socio-cognitive, personal-ethical and pragmatic motives [11]". The main factors influencing learning motivation are:

- Individual characteristics of the learner (age, gender, capability, interests and personal qualities)
- Teacher's attitude towards personal traits and professionalism
- Educational process organized in the educational institution (friendly, free, research-oriented and positive environment created in the community)
- The level of English language proficiency, age, interests and potential of students are taken into account in the publication of textbooks. Along with the development of language skills such as reading, writing, speaking and listening comprehension, it is desirable that the learning materials be based on exercises that encourage students to think creatively and critically.
- Financially and morally support of foreign language specialists in the society and opportunities and benefits provided to language learners

All of the above factors enhance the student's motivation to learn foreign languages, and these motives create a constant movement of the individual towards a specific goal. The first impetus for a student's desire to learn a foreign language is usually appeared in his family by seeing family members' positive attitude towards the learning the language. The more a child is encouraged to learn foreign languages from an early age, the more likely they are to learn one or even two foreign languages by adolescence. It is important to keep in mind that students' motivation to learn a

language should be formed in the family. Undoubtedly, the role of parents in this process is invaluable.

Despite the widespread belief that a student's personality is the most significant aspect in learning and mastering a foreign language, researchers believe that the personality of the teacher is a key and important factor in learning and mastering the language.(Oxford and Shearin, 1994). The role of the teacher and his pedagogical skills is significant in strengthening the desire of students to learn foreign languages. Dornyei (1998) claimed that “motivation is an important factor in educational success” and that teacher proficiency should play a key role in improving the quality of teaching effectiveness. According to Dornyei, personality, competence, teaching methods, and skill of a material, all contribute to a multidimensional component of motivation in language acquisition [12]. Xiao (2012) states that teachers 'personality and knowledge of a topic have an impact on the levels of motivation that students acquire during and even after foreign language classes. A study conducted by Xiao with the help of teachers and students found that 9 out of 10 students had a direct impact on their learning by personal qualities of the teacher. Almost all of the students who participated in the survey answered that the most important characteristics of a teacher that affect students' motivation are “responsibility and passionate about one’s teaching job”. Besides, students included qualities such as “sincerity, patience, support and encouragement to their students” in their list of the most important personal qualities of a teacher that affect student motivation [13]. Xiao believes that difficulties in language acquisition will be significantly alleviated if teachers increase students 'learning motivation using a variety of methods, techniques, and strategies. Xiao also considers that the development of language skills and language learning conditions are determined by motivation, and if teachers start implementing high technology and interactive methods in classes to increase students' interest in language acquisition, students' motivation will be high and long term. Bernard (2010) also confirmed the above

mentioned points and stressed that it is the teachers who are the key figure in helping students develop their language skills based on their interests and aptitude. Bernard conducted research on the importance of motivation among 151 elementary and middle school students and concluded that teachers should not force their students to accomplish the tasks related to the formation of language skills in foreign language classes. From his perspective, language learning activities should be fun and engaging, with activities that will delight the learner. According to Bernard, this criterion of foreign language learning tasks and assignments facilitates language learning activities and subsequently serves to increase students' motivation to learn a foreign language. In his article, Bernard also discusses other factors that affect motivation, one of which is the various activities carried out in the classroom and the other is the general environment in the classroom [14].

The studies which were conducted to investigate the main factors on influencing students' language acquisition motivation shows that besides teachers' and students' positive attitude there are other factors that directly affect language learning motivation. These factors include educational institutions (secondary schools, academic lyceums, colleges, technical schools, higher education institutions), and the learning activities carried out in them. Dornyei and Csizer (1998) have argued that an educational institution is the most conducive place for students to explore their talent, to grow, and develop their motivation to learn foreign languages, among other disciplines. It is here that students are confronted with factors that contribute to their desire to learn a language, as well as its decline or gradual disappearance. The fact that the educational institution provides sufficient conditions for teachers and students to work freely and creatively creates a healthy learning environment in the institutional community. This, in turn, has a positive effect on students' learning motivations.

Due to the fact that academic lyceums operate under the auspices of higher education institutions (HEIs), the educational process and spiritual enlightenment

activities are organized in cooperation, which, of course, helps to increase the external motivation of students. Curricula and programs of foreign languages in the academic lyceum are organized in accordance with the requirements of the CEFR - Common European foreign language learning stages, as defined in the state educational standards. In the system of continuing education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the requirement for graduates of academic lyceums and professional colleges not specializing in foreign languages to acquire foreign languages is "B1" level or 4.5-5.0 scores on the international IELTS score. The requirements for graduates of the group specializing in foreign languages are slightly higher, that is CEFR "B2" level or a minimum requirement of 5.5-6.0 scores in the IELTS system. The goal of teaching a foreign language in all areas of education of an academic lyceum is to form the communicative competence as well as linguistic, sociolinguistic, discursive, strategic, sociocultural, and educational competencies of students [15]. The teaching of foreign languages in Uzbekistan's ongoing education system (secondary schools, academic lyceums and vocational schools, higher education institutions) is intended to be carried out in accordance with international standards, accordingly, the basis of curricula, programs, teaching materials, textbooks, manuals, and teaching methods need to be improved to the standards. Textbooks are also seen as another important factor influencing students' motivation to learn a foreign language. Textbooks and manuals should focus on the development of communicative and linguistic competencies of language learners, as well as it should include exercises and activities that develop language skills such as listening comprehension, speaking, writing, and reading proficiencies. Moreover, the language of the study materials should broaden the general and linguistic outlook of the students based on the study of the history, culture, literature, traditions, and customs of the country where the language is used. In modern English textbooks (which are mostly published by a foreign university press), grammatical rules are preferred to be described using an inductive approach instead of a deductive one.

This is because the inductive approach not only develops students' mental, emotional and motivational skills but also helps them to remember grammatical rules for a long time. The publication of such textbooks, which develop students' worldview, aesthetic taste, independent thinking, work culture, skills of independent learning, is one of the important tasks of the government in improving education.

Another major factor influencing the motivation of students for language acquisition is, definitely, the attitude of the country's elite, the government, to the study of foreign languages in general educational activities. Obviously, Uzbekistan, which is facing the world community under the slogan "New Uzbekistan", has begun to perform radical reforms in the political, social, and economic spheres. The results of the reform are reflected in the education policy, in particular, in the measures aimed at popularizing foreign language learning among the population. In order to increase the motivation of young people to learn foreign languages, the government is adopting a number of decisions and decrees, projects are being implemented. One of them is Presidential Decree PQ-5117 adopted on May 19, 2021 "On measures to bring the promotion of foreign language learning in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level. The resolution specifically instructed to establish an "Agency for the promotion of foreign languages among the population." It was also noted that the schools that have achieved the best results in teaching foreign languages will be rewarded with a gift from the President It is also stated in the decree that for specialists who hold national or international certificates, a monthly allowance will be added to their salary. Students who received a national "B1" certificate or international certificate, for example, like IELTS "6.0" band, will be presented the privilege of the maximum score for the entrance exams of the universities which help the candidates to get the grant for their study. IELTS is an international assessment method for English language competency, and individuals who wish to be evaluated in this system must pay a significant fee. The mechanism, according to the decision, allows students who scored "7.0" or higher to receive the

same amount of money back. Academic lyceum students also are given the opportunity to take a free exam in the second semester. All of those are motivational strategies in the Decree that engage the students' motives to learn English are related to the learners' financial state. Such measures and continued efforts will surely improve pupils' intrinsic motivation to master the language.

Conclusion

To summarize, motivation is critical in language learning. The factors that influence a student's motivation to study a language varies as well. External factors such as parents, family, school, and social events all contribute to an individual's internal motivation. As a result, passive motivation in a student's family is frequently generated by the school teacher's activities. This, in turn, requires a motivational approach from the education sector to increase students 'motivation and interest in language learning in foreign language classes. In addition to the personal qualities of the teacher and the positive attitude towards the student, the learning environment in the classroom, healthy competition among peers and the privileges and opportunities provided for language learning in a society play an important role in increasing students' language learning motivation. A clear example of this is the significant improvement in the quality and effectiveness of language learning as a result of reforms in language learning in Uzbekistan. According to research conducted by leading research institutes, Uzbekistan has been a leader in Central Asia in English language proficiency for the past 5 years[16]. Therefore, unless the factors influencing the motivation of the students are activated, the learner will not become active or his interest in learning the language will end in the short term.

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